

FAIRly Specialist?

Generic vs Disciplinary implications for FAIR-enabling Repositories

Working Paper - IASSIST 2025

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Work that follows on from this IASSIST presentation includes the *FIDELIS Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix (TTRAM)*. With a workshop on June 17th 2025:

<https://eden-fidelis.eu/events/introduction-ttram-matrix-webinar-0>

Introduction

As is somewhat traditional, the answers we were hoping to provide when the abstract was submitted have been replaced by another series of questions.

This informal working paper has been prepared to support the authors' presentation at the 2025 IASSIST Conference. All comments, questions and criticisms are welcome. Share your name and ORCID if you'd like to receive credit on any future revision. The authors will seek to take the outcomes forward at their organisations, and through ongoing activities including the EDEN and FIDELIS Projects¹ and the EOSC Long Term Data Retention Task Force².

Hats and Perspectives

The authors are wearing multiple hats, and their organisations, projects and activities have a variety of relevant perspectives.

Social Sciences

- FSD, the Finnish Social Science Data Archive³
- DANS, Data Archiving and Networked Services in the Netherlands⁴
- UKDS Multi-Partner ESRC Social Science Data Service⁵
- UKDA⁶ Lead Partner and Trustworthy Digital Repository to UKDS
- CESSDA Consortium of Social Science Data Archives⁷ (ERIC)
 - CESSDA Trust & Landscape group⁸
- ESRC Future Data Services⁹

Beyond Social Sciences

- FAIR IMPACT¹⁰ project (now complete)
- EOSC EDEN project on preservation
- FIDELIS, building a network of Trustworthy Repositories.
- EOSC FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects Task Force¹¹
- EOSC Association Long Term Retention Task Force
 - Following on from the EOSC Long Term Preservation Task Force¹²
- OStrails¹³, working on the Commons to Plan-Track-Assess research in EOSC.

¹ <https://eden-fidelis.eu/>

² <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/long-term-data-retention-task-force/>

³ <https://www.fsd.tuni.fi/en/>

⁴ <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/>

⁵ <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/>

⁶ <https://www.data-archive.ac.uk/>

⁷ <https://www.cessda.eu/>

⁸ <https://www.cessda.eu/Core-Working-Groups>

⁹ <https://www.ukri.org/what-we-do/browse-our-areas-of-investment-and-support/future-data-services/>

¹⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/>

¹¹ <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/fair-metrics-and-digital-objects-task-force/>

¹² <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/long-term-data-preservation/>

¹³ <https://ostrails.eu/>

FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, ReUsable

The FAIR Principles¹⁴ actually embody one key 'Principle', that data and metadata (and the authors include all digital objects) should be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable.

This is intended to be achieved through 15 narrow criteria (the 'Principles') with a focus on machine actionability.

FAIR and Repositories

For repositories, including those seeking to be trustworthy digital repositories (TDR), enabling FAIR digital objects has been added¹⁵ to the range of outcomes expected from their retention, curation and preservation of assets relevant to research.

The focus of FAIR on 15 criteria presents a risk that repositories (and funders) may concentrate on these more than the (many) other relevant aspects of findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability.

FAIR assessments are also a 'snapshot' of an object's state; the principles are not time-sensitive (see FAIR+Time, below).

¹⁴ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Sci Data 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

¹⁵ How a European network of FAIR-enabling Trustworthy Data Repositories can align to the vision of EOSC. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7568400>

FAIR Objects, Indicators, Metrics and Tests

The Principles are supported by 'indicators', including those developed through the Research Data Alliance¹⁶.

A wide range of metrics have been developed against these, and other interpretations of the Principles.

These have been used in a range of tools that test FAIRness at a per object level.

HLH-FAIR-AcronymPrinciplesIndicatorsMetricsTests_02_00.vsd

Tests, Objects and Repositories

Tests are applied to individual digital objects including traditional research data, ontologies and software. Repository level characteristics are not assessed, though repositories enable the environment to ensure FAIRness.

Repositories must:

- **maintain** FAIRness from the point of deposit
- **increase** FAIRness during curation and preservation
- avoid changes that **reduce** FAIRness

¹⁶ FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group (2020). FAIR Data Maturity Model: specification and guidelines. Research Data Alliance. DOI: 10.15497/RDA00050

FAIR + Time & Levels of Care

FAIR assessments are a 'snapshot' of an object's state, the principles are not time-sensitive¹⁷, the degree to which FAIR can be maintained over time depends on the level of care provided by the repository¹⁸

Intervention points and time-based guarantees

Beyond basic retention of digital objects for a defined period of time, different repositories provide different levels of care to digital objects:

- Checking compliance at the point of **deposit**
- Ensuring compliance through **initial curation** actions
- Undertaking to maintain compliance over time through **active preservation**

Compliance could be with any defined criteria, including FAIR.

FAIR + Time & Trustworthy Repositories

The CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Digital Repository certification¹⁹ assesses active preservation repositories against 16 criteria across:

- digital object management
- organisational infrastructure
- technology and security

These have been mapped to where enabling the FAIR Principles takes place²⁰.

¹⁷ FAIR + Time: Preservation for a Designated Community (02.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5797776>

¹⁸ Curation & Preservation Levels: CoreTrustSeal Position Paper. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11476980>

¹⁹ CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Digital Repositories Requirements 2023-2025 Extended Guidance (V01.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051096>

²⁰ CoreTrustSeal+FAIR-enabling Capability Maturity Model (v03.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10724060>

Disciplinary FAIR

Through our work on federating research infrastructures towards a European Open Science Cloud²¹ (EOSC) we'll be focussing on how the principles of making digital objects FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable - align with the specialist discipline needs of the social sciences, along with associated tools and tests. During the FAIR IMPACT²² project the developers of F-UJI²³ (a FAIR assessment tool) worked with CESSDA to produce a version of the tool that integrated both generic and disciplinary level tests²⁴.

FAIR, Tests & Dependencies

The Principles range from the more **specific** and **testable** (*F1 'assign an identifier'*), to the more **general** and **aspirational** (*R1 'richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes'*). While some are more explicit about the need for **external references**: *R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards*.

F-UJI, FAIR and CESSDA Social Science Repositories

The generic versus disciplinary approach varied depending on the Principle.

No difference for many:

F1. (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier

This is a broadly applicable technical test that PIDs align with **expected**²⁵ providers

Changes from generic to disciplinary in others:

F2. Data are described with rich metadata

Supports a more narrow and specific test of which of 'core metadata' fields are **expected**.

F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

Disciplinary tests look for a narrower set of **expected** schemas and serialisations.

I2. (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles

R1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

Tests for **expected** discipline-specific vocabularies and data file formats.

²¹

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en

²² D5.1 Implementing metrics for automated FAIR digital objects assessment in a disciplinary context (V1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7784120>, D5.3 - Final recommendations on implementing and exposing FAIR assessment for data and code (V1.0 - Not yet approved by the EC). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15534285>

²³ <https://www.f-uji.net/>

²⁴ Huber, R. (2025). FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics (0.8). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15045911>

²⁵ The significance of 'expected' is covered below in reference to authority for setting expectations.

F-UJI and other FAIR Tests

Applying the tool to sample datasets revealed a number of conclusions:

- Sometimes a generic test is repeated for social science, sometimes an equivalent test is absent.
- Differences in total score models between generic and disciplinary meant social science could score lower. Repositories could just choose a test (or another tool) that scores them higher.
 - There is no standard approach within this tool, or common across the 20+ other FAIR tools, though efforts are being made, including in the OSTrails project²⁶.
- Most support single tests for single objects without batch processing or scaling
- They imply a need for repositories to test at deposit and after curation and preservation actions.

Repositories and FAIR-enabling

There are a number of challenges for repositories seeking to be FAIR-enabling:

- These emerging tests don't address *who has the authority* to say a particular result is **expected**.
 - CESSDA is not a global authority on social science formats, metadata and ontologies.
 - The tests don't support a clear authority model.
- A repository cannot declare that all objects have PIDs because tests are at object level
 - There's no method to test repository level metadata "Yes, we PID all our objects"
- There is no standard guidance on how to expose object metadata for testing
 - Being 'interoperable' with a FAIR Assessment tool isn't a guarantee of general machine-actionability.

A Wider Perspective on Assessment

To enable FAIRness and assess outcomes we need to integrate repositories and their role in digital object assessment into a wider context.

This includes the software and services that support repositories, repository assessment criteria, and the registries that describe objects and repositories²⁷.

²⁷ Diagrams taken from FAIR Ecosystem Components (03.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6726533>

Repositories, Assessment and Discipline

The issues above make it hard for a repository to consistently deploy any FAIR-assessment tool as a part of their production workflows.

- There is clearly a need for guidance on exposing standardised information about repositories and objects to support transparency in general and assessment in particular.
- Any assessment needs to be considered alongside the level of curation and preservation provided.
- FAIR is one of many standards, criteria, requirements, policies, guidance and best practices that repositories are expected to comply with.
 - All of these have different authorities, criteria, metrics and tests.

To Disciplines and Beyond [Domains are not the only fruit]

IASSIST is a social science audience, and the authors here represent social science data archives.

Repository checks on digital objects can include completeness of metadata, ontologies and use of appropriate file formats. These are often seen as key areas where disciplinary repositories will have more specific criteria.

But do these findings also indicate that FAIR Assessment by `'repositories where type = disciplinary'` are an oversimplification of real world scenarios?

Generic and Disciplinary Types

We acknowledge that “generic” repositories are important and necessary to meet the scale of research data, and that their high-level, standardised, and harvestable metadata addresses a need for interoperability that specialist repositories must also support.

But for researchers and funders of disciplinary research we know that the best outcomes for discovery, access, reuse and credit to authors comes from depositing in “disciplinary” repositories.

Ongoing work towards a future FIDELIS network of trustworthy repositories is making it clearer that stating a basic repository type (generic, disciplinary, institutional, national etc) doesn't tell us everything we need to know about them.

Though there is no coherent definition of a generic/generalist repository, should they be described as 'multi-disciplinary'? That question is harder to answer with no single definition of a disciplinary repository beyond self-labelling.

The EDEN project uses the Fields of research and development (FORD)²⁸, but many disciplinary controlled vocabularies exist. The FAIR Principles actually refer to **'domain-relevant'** while the F-UJI metrics refer to a **'target research community'**.

²⁸ <https://uis.unesco.org/node/3079686>

FAIR IMPACT & EDEN Experience

Two quotes from a forthcoming FAIR IMPACT reflection paper are relevant here:

“However, it very quickly became clear that these use case communities were too broad, as FAIR practices differed greatly and sub-communities could easily be identified, for example at **infrastructure and sub-discipline level.**”

“**Preferences for FAIR metrics varied**, with some favouring large **discipline-specific** metrics, others focusing on **data types** or **research methods**, and a smaller group supporting detailed metrics for **sub-disciplines.** ”

Ongoing EDEN project desk research has noted that the disciplinary repositories themselves don't document that a specific approach, process or choice of format, metadata or ontology is for 'discipline-specific reasons'.

Disciplinary-relevant versus Discipline-Specific

The Social Science & Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project²⁹ identified that for the social sciences, particularly for CESSDA associated archives, there are popular, common, standard approaches:

- Data in SPSS and STATA formats supported by
- Metadata in DDI (Data Documentation Initiative) using
- Vocabularies and Ontologies such as the European Languages Social Science Thesaurus (ELSST)

But none of these are strictly limited to Social Sciences. And despite the fact that a lot of FAIR assessment work is focussing on disciplinary needs, the most specific FAIR Principle only states

“R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards”

There are multiple communities and community standards within a single domain. So, before we can agree what a community is, we need a list of disciplines we can all agree on... which will be a subset of a list of agreed domains... which will be a superset of sub-disciplines. This is just intra disciplinary... before anyone mentions multi, cross, inter or trans disciplinary research, and what that actually means for the expectations from repositories.

Qualitative and quantitative research methods represent distinct expertise within Social Science but not unique to Social Sciences. Interviews, surveys and statistical analysis methods have some very specific tools and formats that aren't unique to Social Science. Geography-related formats, metadata and ontologies can be applied across a huge range of scientific research. Social Science researchers frequently record audio and video interviews, but that doesn't make them the go-to source for A/V formats and metadata guidance.

²⁹ SSHOC D3.1 Report on SSHOC (meta)data interoperability problems (v1.0). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3569868>

The picture here is complex and challenging. That doesn't mean good guidance and practices don't exist. But it might mean that "discipline" isn't the only specialist lens on FAIR outcomes, certainly if you want to write a nice binary pass/fail coded test.

Domain/Discipline, methodologies and content types all play a role and may have different sources of expert guidance. These can also interact e.g. best practice guidance on A/V quality for TV broadcast may not be the best standard to apply to social science interview recordings.

Types, Categories and Variables

Beyond being 'a specialist' (e.g. disciplinary) repository, we need to understand what variables influence which researchers can deposit and access digital objects, and how the characteristics of digital objects are used to permit or restrict their deposit or access. These characteristics include disciplinary scope, but also include and interact with research methods, content types, file formats, metadata schemas and ontologies.

Depending on the level of curation and preservation expected by funders, depositors and reusers of digital objects, these factors all influence the repository activities, functions and required expertise.

Conclusions, Communication and Choices

As noted above, a basic repository type (generic, disciplinary, institutional, national etc) doesn't tell us everything we need to know about them.

The most pressing of these seems to be to identify

- WHO can deposit/access
- WHICH objects in
- WHAT repositories

This depends on understanding the characteristics (and defining and sharing relevant metadata) about repositories, depositors and users as well as digital objects.

We need a more sophisticated approach to the different specialisms and fortes that influence repository activities and functions, including discipline and domain, but also methods, object types, file formats/serialisations, schemas and ontologies. Repositories are under increasing pressure to share more information to demonstrate they comply with multiple criteria, so cooperative approaches and common registries are needed.

And finally, we need an acknowledgement that a wide range of different standards, governance and community bodies are creating criteria that set rules for repositories. No single binary test outcome defining a repository as trustworthy or FAIR-enabling is possible. Indicators, metrics and tests all need to take account of the different 'authorities' with their own perspectives and expectations.

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³⁰ <https://www.data-archive.ac.uk/>

³¹ <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/>

³² <https://www.essex.ac.uk/about/faculty-of-social-sciences>

³³ <https://www.fsd.tuni.fi/en/>

³⁴ <https://www.tuni.fi/en>

³⁵ <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/>